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Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III) and Os(IV) with 4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-Penten-2-One

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A large number of β -ketoimines¹⁻⁵ are known. They act as bidentate ligands and serve as very good chelating agents. Numerous transition metal complexes of β -ketoimines have been studied by various workers⁶⁻⁹. This communication deals with complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III) and Os(IV) ions with a bidentate Schiff's base derived from *p*-dimethylamino-aniline and acetyl acetone, known as 4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One (DIMAPO).

Experimental

All chemicals and reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Preparation of 4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One :

This was formed by condensing an ethereal soln. of *p*-dimethylamino-aniline and freshly distilled acetyl acetone on water bath (45°-50°) and evaporating off ether. The amine was prepared from *p*-nitroso dimethyl aniline¹⁰ and the latter was obtained from dimethyl aniline¹¹.

Preparation and Isolation of Complexes :

Bis-[4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One]-copper(II), *Diaquo bis*-[4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One]-Ni(II) and Co(II) - 20 ml of 0.1M solutions of the metal chloride in 95% ethanol were treated with the ligand. The pH of the soln. was raised by addition of aq. ammonia(2N). The black (Cu), sky blue (Ni) and buff grey (Co) precipitates formed after filtering, washing with water and a little ethanol, were dried. The complexes are slightly soluble in common organic solvents. The copper and cobalt complexes do not melt, the nickel complex melts at 208°. Formula :

[Cu(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₂] Anal. calcd : Cu : 12.77%, C : 62.70%, H : 6.83% and N : 11.21%, Found : Cu : 12.60%, C : 62.56%, H : 6.90% and N : 11.32%. [Ni(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₂·(H₂O)₂] Anal. calcd : Ni : 11.11%, C : 58.76%, H : 7.53%, N : 10.54%, Found : Ni : 10.94%, C : 58.58%, H : 7.68%, N : 10.32%.

[Co(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₂·(H₂O)₂] Anal. calcd : Co : 11.14%, C : 58.98%, H : 7.18%, N : 10.59%, Found : Co : 10.89%, C : 58.68%, H : 6.98%, N : 10.30%.

Tris-[4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One]-Fe(III) - 40 ml of 0.1M soln. of anhydrous ferric chloride in 95% ethanol was treated with the ligand. An intense brown colour was formed. The soln. was concentrated on a water bath and cooled. A brown precipitate was formed by the addition of a little 0.1 M aq. sodium hydroxide soln. It was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. m.p. 110°. It is soluble in absolute alcohol, acetone and benzene. Formula : [Fe(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₃] Anal. calcd : Fe : 7.9%, C : 66.21%, H : 7.21%, N : 11.88%. Found : Fe : 7.82%, C : 66.40%, H : 7.01%, N : 11.72%.

Tetra Kis-[4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One]-Os(IV) dihydrate - The grey crystalline precipitate was formed by refluxing osmium tetrachloride soln. with the ligand in the ratio 1 : 4 (M : L) and 3-4 ml of aqueous dil. ammonia soln. for 1½ hr and subsequent cooling. The precipitate was filtered, washed with distilled water and a little acetone and dried in vacuum over anhydrous P₂O₅; m.p. above 300°. The complex compound is slightly soluble in acetone and absolute alcohol. Formula : [Os(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₄·2H₂O] Anal. calcd : Os : 17.38%, C : 56.78%, H : 6.91%, N : 10.19%. Found : Os : 17.18%, C : 56.56%, H : 6.80%, N : 9.98%.

Results and Discussion

Cu(L)₂ : The electronic spectrum of the copper complex, Cu(L)₂ (L = DIMAPO), is consistent with an essentially tetrahedral structure. The d-d bands for a planar structure occur in the range 14000-18000 cm⁻¹, whereas tetrahedral complexes possess a broad band in the region 15000 cm⁻¹ and a strong

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band near 22000 cm⁻¹. The complex shows a band at 15400 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder around 21600 cm⁻¹ which support tetrahedral stereochemistry.

The magnetic moment of the complex is 2.0 B.M. showing thereby tetrahedral geometry around the ion¹²⁻¹³.

[Ni(L)₂(H₂O)₂]: The electronic spectrum of the nickel complex shows bands at 8900 cm⁻¹ (ν₁), 113000 cm⁻¹ (ν₁'), 14700 cm⁻¹ (ν₂), 16600 cm⁻¹ (ν₁''), 25700 cm⁻¹ (ν₃) and 26300 cm⁻¹ (ν₁'''), a characteristic of a distorted octahedral environment¹⁴, ν are assigned to transitions ³B_{1g}→³E_g, ³B_{1g}→³B_{2g}, ³B_{1g}→³A_{2g}, ³B_{1g}→³E_g, ³B_{1g}→³A_{2g}, ³B_{1g}→³E_g.

Calculated parameters in cm⁻¹ are 10D_q (1130), D_x (514), D_t (274), Δ₁ (171), Δ₂ (3426), B (913) and β=0.87. Further the ratio ν₂/ν₁ comes to 1.6, showing octahedral coordination in this complex¹⁵.

The Ni(II) complex has a magnetic moment 3.25 B.M., which is well within the range for an octahedral complex.

[Co(L)₂(H₂O)₂]: The electronic spectrum of the Co(II) complex shows four bands in the region 8000-9890, 17000-20000, 21707-26300, 30000-38000 cm⁻¹, characteristic of octahedral geometry. They are assigned to the transitions ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(F) (ν₃).

A broad band at 8600 cm⁻¹ with a weak shoulder around 7800 cm⁻¹ and few closely spaced but intense bands are observed at 18400, 20300, 30000 and 36000 cm⁻¹.

The lower energy band at 8600 cm⁻¹ is assigned to transition ν₁, whereas the bands at 18400 and 20300 cm⁻¹ are the components of the ν₂ band. This nature of the ν₂ band is very common in Co(II) complexes and may be due to the spin-forbidden transition or to the low symmetry of the ligand-field components¹⁶. The bands at 30000 and 36800 cm⁻¹ are the charge transfer bands. The parameters calcd. using Figgis eqn.¹⁵ are D_q=1006 cm⁻¹, B=1048 cm⁻¹, β=0.93 and L.F.S.E.=17.24 kK/mole. These values suggest a highly distorted octahedral geometry around Co(II) ion^{17a,17b}.

Fe(L)₃: The electronic spectrum of the complex shows five bands at 14800, 17800, 25960, 28640 and 37980 cm⁻¹, which are assigned to the transitions ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}, ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{2g}, t_{2g}→π*, π←e_g, π←π*. The first two are d-d transitions and the rest are charge transfer bands.

The well-resolved bands are consequently assigned to the following transitions: t_{2g}←π*

(25960), π←e_g (28640), π←π* (37980 cm⁻¹). The values of 10 D_q obtained by D_q/B=1.1 and B & β come out to 6776 and 616 cm⁻¹ and 0.47 respectively.

F₂ and F₄ (the free Fe⁺³ ion values) are respectively 80.93 and 50.27 kK. In the complex under study these values are reduced to 55.12 and 44.85 kK (from the free ion value), showing the distorted Oh symmetry.

In octahedral environment Fe(III) forms either high-spin or low-spin type complexes. The magnetic moment of the present complex is 5.95 B.M., i.e., with five unpaired electrons and an octahedral configuration.

Os(L)₄.2H₂O: The electronic spectrum shows four bands (18200, 20400, 32600, 41210 cm⁻¹) all of which are likely to be charge transfer type. The complex is a diamagnetic.

I. R. Spectra: I.R. spectrum of the ligand exhibits characteristic bands at 3525 and 2780 cm⁻¹ due to ν OH vibrations (involving intramolecular hydrogen bonding). The νC=N of the ligand occurs at 1650 cm⁻¹.

The bands due to νOH vibrations in the free ligand are not observed in the complexes. This suggests that the hydroxyl group of the ligand is involved in coordination. νC=N of the ligand occurring at 1650 cm⁻¹ was shifted to lower frequency side on complexation showing the participation of the azomethine nitrogen in coordination.

In Ni⁺² and Co⁺² complexes broad band around 3300, 1270 cm⁻¹ due to ν(OH) and δ(OH) of water molecule appear. On heating the complexes above 120° water molecule is not lost showing that it is the coordinated and not the lattice held.

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First Dissociation Constant of Succinic Acid from 0° to 50° by e.m.f. Method Based on Modified Davies Equation

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PINCHING and Bates¹ measured the e.m.f. of the cells of the type,

and calculated first dissociation constant, K_1 of succinic acid from 0° to 50° at 5 degrees interval. Since, K_1/K_2 for succinic acid is about 25, they used many approximations in the calculation for overlapping equilibria. Moreover, the method of computation of first dissociation constant was much complicated.

In the present communication, values for K_1 from 0° to 50° at 5 degrees interval were recalculated on the basis of modified Davies equation proposed by Prasad².

Results and Discussion

The electromotive force of the cell (C-1) can be given by

$$m_{\text{H}^+} = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{(E^\circ - E)F}{2.30259RT} + \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \log m_{\text{Cl}^-} - \beta\mu \right] \dots (1)$$

Here, β for the cell (C-1) containing solution of HCl and NaHSuc will have the same value as in pure HCl, provided the ionic strength, μ does not exceed beyond 0.2³⁻⁴. The reaction between H^+ and HSuc^- ions in cell (C-1) cannot go to

completion because of dissociation of molecular succinic acid (H_2Suc).

Further, the hydrogen ion concentration, m_{H^+} is not large enough in cell (C-1) to prevent the second step dissociation,

From application of electrical neutrality in solutions of the cell (C-1),

$$m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{Suc}^-} + m_{\text{Cl}^-} = m_{\text{H}^+} + m_{\text{Na}^+}$$

It follows,

$$m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{Suc}^-} = m_{\text{H}^+} + 0.5 \text{ m} \dots (4)$$

Equation (3) can be represented by

$$\frac{m_{\text{Suc}^-}}{m_{\text{HSuc}^-}} = \text{antilog} \left[(\log K_2 - \beta_2\mu) + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \log m_{\text{H}^+} \right] \dots (5)$$

For computation of molalities of separate entity present in cell (C-1), an arbitrary value was assigned to μ in equation (1) and the corresponding value for m_{H^+} was found out. In the above recalculation, E° due to Harned & Ehlers⁵, β due to Sinha, Ghosh & Prasad⁶ and E due to Pinching & Bates¹ were taken. The value of m_{H^+} thus obtained was fed into equations (4) and (5) and the corresponding values for m_{HSuc^-} and m_{Suc^-} were calculated. Values for $\log K_2$ and β_2 for equation (5) were taken from author's earlier work⁶.

Since the ionic strength, μ of solution in cell (C-1) is given by,

$$\mu = 1.75 \text{ m} + 1.5 m_{\text{H}^+} - 0.5 m_{\text{HSuc}^-} \dots (6)$$

a fresh value for μ was calculated by substituting the above values. This fresh value of μ was again fed in equation (1) and the corresponding value of m_{H^+} was calculated. The above process of successive approximation was repeated till constancy in values for m_{H^+} , m_{HSuc^-} , m_{Suc^-} and μ were obtained up to 6th place of decimal. The value of $m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}}$ was calculated from equation (7) obtained from the consideration of total succinate entities present in cell (C-1),

$$1.5 \text{ m} = m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + m_{\text{Suc}^-} + m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}} \dots (7)$$

The equilibrium (2) can be represented by

$$\log \frac{m_{\text{H}^+} - m_{\text{HSuc}^-}}{m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}}} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_1 - \beta_1\mu \dots (8)$$

where K_1 is the first dissociation constant and $\beta_1 = (\beta_{\text{H}^+} + \beta_{\text{HSuc}^-})$. The L.H.S. of equation (8) were plotted against μ , when straight lines were obtained

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